

STRIDER Canada Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) Charter

STRIDER Canada: A randomised controlled trial of sildenafil therapy in dismal prognosis early-onset intrauterine growth restriction (Canada).

UBC CW REB: H15-00899

STRIDER Canada is an investigator-initiated multicentre placebo controlled randomised trial of sildenafil therapy. STRIDER Canada will recruit women with an early-onset IUGR and low Serum PIGF levels (< 5th percentile for gestational age) across Maternal Fetal Medicine (MFM) centres in Canada. STRIDER Canada trial is led by a team of investigators based at the STRIDER Trial Coordinating Centre at the University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada (Dr Peter von Dadelszen, Dr Kenneth Lim, Dr Laura Magee, and Dr Sayrin Lalji). These investigators are working in collaboration with other similar studies planned worldwide (STRIDER NZAus, STRIDER UK, Dutch STRIDER, and STRIDER Ireland) and data will contribute to a planned individual patient data (IPD) analysis. Dr. Peter von Dadelszen is a Co-Leader and is a member of the IPD collaboration. This document describes the roles and responsibilities of the DSMB for the STRIDER Canada trial only.

Data Safety Monitoring Board members:

Chair:

Dr. Gideon Koren, Professor of Pediatrics, Pharmacology, Pharmacy and Medical Genetics, The University of Toronto.

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Members:

Dr. Howard Berger, St. Michael's Hospital

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Dr. William A. Grobman, Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine

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Dr. Joan Crane, Eastern health.

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Aims:

The DSMB is responsible for safeguarding the interests of the STRIDER Canada trial participants, assessing trial safety and monitor the overall conduct of the clinical trial.

Reporting:

The DSMB will report to the STRIDER Canada Lead Investigator team. If required they will also liaise with the STRIDER IPD Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB).

Data Collection and Management:

STRIDER Canada will use an electronic data capturing system based at Child and Family Research Institute (CFRI) and St. Pauls Hospital, Vancouver. All data will be stored electronically using a unique study Id. There are no pre-planned interim analyses.

Responsibilities of the DSMB:

1. The DSMB will receive regular reports from STRIDER Trial Coordinating Centre including data on recruitment, individual study site compliance and safety data.
2. The DSMB will be notified of all serious adverse events directly by a member of the STRIDER Trial Coordinating Centre.
3. The DSMB will have direct access to the UBC data management team to reveal treatment code in the event that an adverse event or serious adverse event is deemed to be related to treatment.
4. The DSMB will make recommendations to the Lead Investigator Team with regard to early cessation of the trial due to strong evidence of adverse effect/harm (as a result of a serious adverse event or multiple adverse events deemed specifically related to treatment).
5. The DSMB will advise the Lead Investigator Team on operational procedures affecting recruitment, treatment, and follow-up.

The Chairperson will:

- a. Chair DSMB meetings.
- b. Facilitate and summarise meeting discussion.
- c. Keep minutes of the DSMB meetings securely.
- d. Provide a written report to Lead Investigator Team

The Trial Statistician/data analyst may take the minutes of the closed session of DSMB meetings if requested by DSMB.

Meetings:

DSMB meetings will be arranged by the STRIDER Trial Coordinating Centre on a date suitable for all members to attend. The DSMB may meet at least twice yearly (in-person or by teleconference) or as needed. Additional meetings may be requested/required in the event of issues of concern arising. As there are five members, at least three members are requested to participate in all meetings to provide a quorum. DSMB can request whether a meeting should be an open or closed session or both.

A representative of the STRIDER Trial Coordinating Centre (typically the Trial Co-ordinator) shall prepare a standard agenda and a study summary for each meeting including recruitment

figures, status of sites and details of any issues. The Trial Statistician will prepare open and closed reports (as per DSMB request).

All members of the DSMB shall participate in discussions and voting. Every effort shall be made to reach a unanimous decision. Minutes may be taken by a nominated member of the DSMB or trial coordinator and kept securely by the Chairperson.

Recommendations open to the DSMB:

Possible recommendations may include,

1. No action needed, trial continues as planned.
2. Early stopping of the trial if there is proof beyond reasonable doubt that the treatment causes harm or benefit (based on at least other two STRIDER trials results). Trial sequential analysis, developed by the Copenhagen Trial Unit will be conducted first when two STRIDER trials are completed, and then again as each additional trial is completed. In each iteration of the trial sequential analysis, the effect size of the combined trial data (diversity-adjusted required information size) will be calculated, and evidence of harm or benefit will be assessed (<http://www.ctu.dk/tsa/>). The Umbrella DSMB will be formed and will review results for effectiveness, safety and futility and may advise stopping on-going trials based on any of these criteria -
 - For effectiveness – risk reduction acceptable for stopping will be 50% at 5% significance level
 - For safety – risk reduction acceptable for stopping will be 20% at 1% significance level
 - For futility – risk reduction acceptable for stopping will be 20% at 1% significance level

Reporting to the Lead Investigator Team:

A report of the DSMB recommendations will be sent to the Lead Investigator Team within two weeks of each DSMB meeting.

Disagreement between DSMB and the Lead Investigator Team:

If the DSMB has serious concerns with a Lead Investigator Team decision following DSMB recommendations, a meeting of these two groups will be held. If required confidential data may be revealed to all those attending such a meeting. The meeting will be chaired by an external expert not directly involved with the trial and who is agreed upon by both the Chair of the DSMB and the Principal Investigator.